

ADMINISTRATORS PROMOTION APPRAISAL PRACTICES AS CORRELATES OF LECTURERS JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN RIVERS STATE

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Abstract: The study investigated administrators' promotion appraisal practices as correlates of lecturers' job performance in public universities in Rivers State. Three objectives, three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study was 3525 academic staff in public Universities in Rivers State. A sample size of 881 academic staff representing 25% of the entire population was derived through the stratified random sampling technique. Two different self-structured questionnaires titled: "Administrators Promotion Appraisal Practices Questionnaire" and "Lecturers Job Performance Questionnaire" which were on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree were used as instruments for the study. The instruments were face and content validated by two experts from Measurement and Evaluation and the Department of Educational Management respectively in Rivers State University and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded reliability indexes of 0.86, 0.85, 0.83 and 0.88 with the overall reliability coefficient of 0.86. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used to answer research questions while the t-ratio transformation statistic was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there is a moderate positive relationship between lecturers' research publications and their job performances in public universities in Rivers State. It was concluded that the findings of this study highlighted the significant relationships between various promotion appraisal practices and lecturers' job performance in public universities in Rivers State. It was recommended among others that Public universities in Rivers State should develop and implement clear and transparent promotion appraisal criteria that recognize and reward lecturers' research publications and contributions within their academic disciplines.

Keywords: Administrators Promotion Appraisal Practices, Lecturers Job Performance, Lecturers' Research Publication, Lecturers' Community Services, Lecturers' Supervision of Students

Introduction

Public universities play a key role in the educational system of Rivers State, Nigeria, and indeed, globally. These institutions serve as hubs for knowledge dissemination, research and intellectual discourse, contributing significantly to societal development. In Nigeria, like in many other countries, the quality of education provided by public universities is contingent upon various factors, including the effectiveness of administrators and the job performances of lecturers. Administrators in public universities in Rivers State are responsible for overseeing

institutional policies, managing resources, and creating conducive environments for teaching, learning, and research. Their roles extended to the evaluation and appraisal of faculty members, including lecturers, to ensure accountability, efficiency, and productivity in the school system. Lecturers' growth and development in the academic environment depends on the appraisal practices of the administrator.

The impact of appraisal practices on lecturers' job performance is also contingent upon the support structures and professional development opportunities available within the academic environment (Eze & Chukwu, 2018). Administrators play a crucial role in fostering a culture of continuous improvement and learning by providing resources, training, and mentorship to lecturers based on the outcomes of the appraisal process (Okeke, 2020). The nature and effectiveness of appraisal practices significantly shape lecturers' perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors within public universities (Onyia & Nwachukwu, 2019). By recognizing the importance of fair and transparent appraisal systems, administrators can contribute to the enhancement of lecturers' job performance and the overall quality of higher education in Rivers State and beyond. Effective appraisal systems provide feedback mechanisms that enable lecturers to identify areas for improvement, capitalize on strengths, and align their activities with institutional goals and objectives. Conversely, ineffective or inadequate appraisal practices may lead to demotivation, disengagement, and suboptimal job performances among lecturers.

An appraisal system is a systematic process of determining an employee's performance level. It identifies the individual's areas of strength and weakness. Omotayo and Omotayo (2019) asserted that the appraisal system measures skills and accomplishments with reasonable accuracy and uniformity which provides a way to help identify areas for performance enhancement and to help promote professional growth. According to Obasi and Ohia in Ojo and Ayodele (2020), appraisal system is the process of evaluating how well employees perform their jobs as compared to a set of standards and then communicating that information to those employees. The process is to recognize achievement, evaluate job progress and then design training for further development of skills and strength. Specifically, it identifies the gap between the expected and actual performance levels. Santiago and Benavides (2016), maintained that appraisal system can be interlinked with institution arrangements to improve the teaching process. They further added that results from the appraisal system could be used to identify teaching needs and contribute to the definition of the school plan to improve the teaching process in the school.

The appraisal system is an essential constituent of the whole human resource management function in institutions of higher learning (Adewale & Adegunle, 2018). The appraisal system is based on setting agreed performance targets, work planning, reporting, and feedback. The general objective of the appraisal system is to improve and manage the workers' performance. Improving and managing the performance of workers/employees would enable an advanced level of staff involvement and participation in the delivery, evaluation, and planning of work performance. Adewale and Adegunle (2018) reiterated that the appraisal system should consist of the following: performance targets, work planning, values, monitoring, competency assessment, evaluation and end-of-year appraisal. Likewise, they noted that a lecturer should improve his organization's professionalism and performance standards to the extent appropriate for his office.

Studies have shown that appraisal systems can positively impact lecturers' job performance and motivation (Okorie & Nwaogu, 2020). When appraisal practices are transparent, fair, and aligned with institutional goals, lecturers are more likely to perceive the evaluation process as credible and meaningful (Okafor, 2019). This perception, in turn, can foster a sense of accountability and commitment among lecturers towards their professional responsibilities (Nwagwu, 2016). Conversely, ineffective or arbitrary appraisal practices can have detrimental effects on lecturers' job performances (Ofoegbu & Egbule, 2019). When appraisal systems lack clarity, consistency, or objectivity, lecturers may experience feelings of demotivation, disillusionment, and disengagement (Okafor & Uche, 2018). Moreover, if appraisal processes are perceived as punitive or biased, lecturers may become resistant to feedback and less inclined to invest effort in their teaching, research, or administrative duties (Oyibocho & Ekeh, 2017). University administrators utilize a range of appraisal practices to evaluate the job performance of lecturers, thus influencing the overall effectiveness of the academic environment. Okafor (2019), stated that appraisal practices utilized by administrators include lecturers' research publication, lecturers' community services, lecturers' supervision of students etc.

Research as an appraisal practice holds significant weight in academic institutions, often epitomized by the adage "publish or perish." In the context of administrators' appraisal practices in public universities, research productivity is a crucial criterion used to assess the job performances of lecturers. Adeleke and Okoro (2020) stated that administrators often prioritize research output as a key indicator of academic success and contribution to knowledge generation within their institutions. These quantitative indicators provide administrators with tangible evidence of lecturers' scholarly contributions and impact within their respective fields. The quantity and quality of publications, including peer-reviewed articles, books, and conference presentations, grants secured and contributions to scholarly literature are commonly used as an appraisal practice to evaluate lecturers' job performance. Administrators often set expectations for lecturers to engage in scholarly research and publish their findings in referred journals. These expectations are often integrated into performance evaluation criteria and job descriptions, reflecting the institution's commitment to academic excellence and research-driven scholarship. Smith and Brown (2019) suggest that lecturers who actively engage in research are better equipped to incorporate new knowledge and perspectives into their teaching, thereby enriching the learning experience for students. Ogunbajo and Adewale (2019) opined that engagement in research enables lecturers to stay abreast of developments in their fields, deepen their expertise, and contribute to the advancement of knowledge. Through conducting research, lecturers develop critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, and subject matter expertise, which enrich their teaching and mentorship capabilities. Moreover, research activities facilitate collaboration and networking opportunities both within and outside the university, enabling lecturers to exchange ideas, share best practices, and establish partnerships for interdisciplinary research projects. As lecturers produce scholarly publications, present at conferences, and secure research grants, they enhance the reputation and visibility of their departments and the university as a whole. Thus, research serves as a cornerstone of lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State, driving academic excellence, innovation, and societal impact.

Community service is a vital aspect of lecturers' appraisal practices in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. It involves voluntary engagements that contribute positively to local communities and society at large. Lecturers actively participate in various community service initiatives to address societal needs and foster development. Community service as an appraisal practice holds significance in the evaluation framework of lecturers' job performances in academic institutions (Eze & Chukwu, 2018). Administrators often integrate community service as a criterion for assessing the holistic contributions of lecturers to the university's mission and the broader society. Community service serves as a vital indicator of lecturers' engagement and impact beyond the confines of the academic setting. Administrators recognize the importance of fostering strong university-community relations and promoting social responsibility among lecturers. Lecturers are encouraged to participate in various community service activities, including outreach programs, volunteer initiatives, and partnerships with local organizations and stakeholders (Oyibocho & Ekeh, 2017). These activities reflect the university's commitment to civic engagement, social justice, and community development. Administrators evaluate lecturers' involvement in community service as part of their overall job performance assessment. They consider the scope, duration, and impact of community service activities in determining the extent to which lecturers contribute to the university's outreach efforts and fulfill their responsibilities as engaged citizens and educators. Adeleke and Okoro (2020) asserted that by working closely with local organizations, government agencies, and non-profit groups, lecturers demonstrate their commitment to social responsibility and community engagement. Community service serves as a meaningful appraisal practice for lecturers in public universities in Rivers State. By actively engaging in community service activities, lecturers demonstrate their commitment to social responsibility, contribute to the welfare of local communities, and enhance their reputation within the academic community and society at large. Supervision of students serves as a crucial appraisal practice in public universities across Nigeria, including Rivers State. Supervision of students encompasses various activities such as mentoring, advising, and guiding students in their academic and research endeavors (Adebayo & Okafor, 2018). Lecturers are expected to demonstrate effective supervisory skills in nurturing students' intellectual growth, fostering critical thinking, and facilitating their successful completion of academic programs. The supervision of students also extends to research supervision, where lecturers oversee the research projects, theses, and dissertations of undergraduate and graduate students (Okeke & Mohammed, 2020). Administrators assess lecturers' abilities to provide constructive feedback, mentorship, and guidance to students in conducting research and producing scholarly work. Furthermore, the supervision of students serves as a key indicator of lecturers' commitment to academic excellence, students' success, and the mission of the university (Oluwaseun & Afolabi, 2019). Administrators recognize the importance of fostering a supportive learning environment where students can thrive academically and professionally under the guidance of dedicated lecturers. Supervision of students provides lecturers with opportunities to demonstrate their expertise, knowledge, and mentorship abilities. As lecturer's guide and support students through their academic projects, they showcase their capacity to impart knowledge, provide guidance, and facilitate learning experiences. Effective supervision requires lecturers to demonstrate strong communication skills, subject matter expertise, and the ability to provide constructive feedback, all of which are essential components of effective

teaching and mentorship. Lecturers who actively supervise students' research endeavors enhance their own research profiles, publications, and scholarly contributions, thereby bolstering their academic reputation and standing within the university community (Okonkwo & Ibrahim, 2017).

Statement of the Problem

In public universities in Rivers State, the way lecturers are evaluated for promotions and performance has a big influence on their work and the quality of education. Key aspects of a lecturer's job, such as doing research, participating in community service, taking on leadership roles, supervising students, joining professional organizations, and maintaining academic standards, are often not properly recognized or rewarded. In the academic system, lecturers face numerous challenges that impede their ability to fulfill the rigorous demands of appraisal practices (Emene 2019).

Consequently, it has been observed that lecturers are compelled to prioritize meeting appraisal criteria over dedicating time and resources to scholarly endeavors, leading to diminished job performances in teaching and compromised educational outcomes for students. The critical need to explore the underlying factors driving the pressure on lecturers to meet the demands for appraisal in the university system emphasizes the urgency of investigating administrators' promotion appraisal practices and their influence on lecturers' job performance. The harsh economic realities, coupled with the exigencies of appraisal practices, necessitate a comprehensive examination of the issues affecting the academic workforce. Therefore, this study endeavors to elucidate the intricate dynamics between administrators' promotion appraisal practices and lecturers' job performance in public universities in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the administrators' promotion appraisal practices as correlates of lecturers' job performance in public universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between lecturers' research publication as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State.
2. Examine the relationship between lecturers' community services as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State.
3. Ascertain the relationship between lecturers' supervision of students as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between lecturers' research publication as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between lecturers' community services as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between lecturers' supervision of students as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

- Ho₁ There is no significant relationship between lecturers' research publication as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State.
- Ho₂ There is no significant relationship between lecturers' community services as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State.
- Ho₃ There is no significant relationship between lecturers' supervision of students as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Methodology

This study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study was 3525 academic staff of the Universities in Rivers State which consists of 1385 academic staff of University of Port Harcourt, 1705 academic staff of Rivers state university and 435 academic staff of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The sample size of 881 consisting of 346 academic staff of University of Port Harcourt (UNIPORT), 426 academic staff of Rivers State University (RSU), and 109 academic staff of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) was derived through stratified random sampling technique. Two different questionnaires titled: "Administrators' Promotion Appraisal Practices Questionnaire (APAPQ)" and "Lecturers' Job Performance Questionnaire (LJPQ)" which were on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree were used for data collection. The instruments were face and content validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation and the Department of Educational Management. The instruments were tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded reliability indexes of 0.86, 0.85, 0.83 and 0.88 with the overall reliability coefficient of 0.86. A total of 881 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the academic staff from the three Universities used in the study by the researcher and two (2) trained research assistants. However, due to poor accessibility and availability on several visits to the respondents for collection, only 714 (81% rate) were retrieved and this proportion was used for the analysis. Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics was used to answer the research questions. The relationship value of 0.1 – 0.4 was counted as "low correlation", 0.5 denote "moderate correlation" while 0.6 – 0.9 denote "high correlation". The hypotheses were tested using t- ratio transformation at 0.05 level of significance with a critical t-value of ± 1.96 . Analyzed data therefore with t-Transformed value above the t-critical value of ± 1.96 was rejected and below was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between lecturers' research publication as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Lecturers’ Research Publication as an Administrators’ Promotion Appraisal Practice and Lecturers’ Job Performances in Public Universities in Rivers State.

			Lecturers’ Research Publications	Lecturers’ Performance	Job Level Correlation	of
Lecturers’ Publications	Research	Pearson Correlation	1	.574**		
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000		
		N	714	714	Moderate and	
Lecturers’ Performance	Job	Pearson Correlation	.574**	1		Positive
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			Relationship
		N	714	714		

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 revealed a correlation value of $r = 0.574$. This value is moderate and positive, thus indicating that there is moderate and positive relationship between lecturers’ research publication as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State. This result implies that lecturers’ research publication administrators’ promotion appraisal practice relates with lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between lecturers’ community services as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Lecturers’ Community Services as an Administrators’ Promotion Appraisal Practice and Lecturers’ Job Performances in Public Universities in Rivers State.

			Lecturers’ Community Services	Lecturers’ Performance	Job Level Correlation	of
Lecturers’ services	community	Pearson Correlation	1	.501**		
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000		
		N	714	714	Moderate and	
Lecturers’ Performance	Job	Pearson Correlation	.501**	1		Positive
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			Relationship
		N	714	714		

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Data on Table 2 revealed a correlation value of $r = 0.501$. This value is moderate and positive, thus indicating that there is moderate and positive relationship between lecturers’ community services as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State. This result implies that lecturers’ community services administrators’ promotion appraisal practice relates with lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between lecturers’ supervision of students as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State?

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Lecturers’ Supervision of Students as an Administrators’ Promotion Appraisal Practice and Lecturers’ Job Performances in Public Universities in Rivers State.

		Lecturers’ Supervision of Students	Lecturers’ Performance	Job Level of Correlation
Lecturers’ Supervision of Students	Pearson Correlation	1	.750**	High and Positive Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	714	714	
Lecturers’ Job Performance	Pearson Correlation	.750**	1	High and Positive Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	714	714	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 revealed a correlation value of $r = 0.750$. This value is high and positive, thus indicating that there is high and positive relationship between lecturers’ supervision of students as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State. This result implies that lecturers’ supervision of students administrators’ promotion appraisal practice relates with lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Hypotheses

Ho₁ There is no significant relationship between lecturers’ research publication as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of t-ratio Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between Lecturers’ Research Publication as an Administrators’ Promotion Appraisal Practice and Lecturers’ Job Performances in Public Universities in Rivers State.

Variables	N	Df	r-value	t-Trans.	t-crit.	α	Decision
Lecturers’ Publications	714			26.66			Ho ₁ Rejected
		712	0.574		±1.96	0.05	Significant Relationship Exist
Lecturers’ Job Performance	714						

Table 4 above showed a t-ratio Transformation value of 26.66 which was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 712. Since the t-Transformation value of 26.66 was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between lecturers’ research publication as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State was rejected and the alternative upheld which states that there is a significant relationship between lecturers’ research publication as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State. This implies that a significant relationship exist between lecturers’ research publication as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Ho₂ There is no significant relationship between lecturers’ community services as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Table 5: Summary of t-ratio Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between Lecturers’ Community Services as an Administrators’ Promotion Appraisal Practice and Lecturers’ Job Performances in Public Universities in Rivers State.

Variables	N	Df	r-value	t-Trans.	t-crit.	α	Decision
Lecturers’ Services	714			26.68			Ho ₂ Rejected
		712	0.501		±1.96	0.05	Significant Relationship Exist
Lecturers’ Job Performance	714						

Table 5 above showed a t-ratio Transformation value of 26.68 which was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 712. Since the t-Transformation value of 26.68 was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between lecturers’

community services as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State was rejected and the alternative upheld which states that there is a significant relationship between lecturers’ community services as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State. This implies that a significant relationship exist between lecturers’ community services as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Ho₃ There is no significant relationship between lecturers’ supervision of students as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Table 6: Summary of t-ratio Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between Lecturers’ Supervision of Students as an Administrators’ Promotion Appraisal Practice and Lecturers’ Job Performances in Public Universities in Rivers State.

Variables	N	Df	r-value	t-Trans.	t-crit.	α	Decision
Lecturers’ Supervision of Students	714			26.69			Ho ₂ Rejected
		712	0.750		±1.96	0.05	Significant Relationship Exist
Lecturers’ Job Performance	714						

Table 6 above showed a t-ratio Transformation value of 26.69 which was greater than the t-critical value of ±1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 712. Since the t-Transformation value of 26.69 was greater than the t-critical value of ±1.96, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between lecturers’ supervision of students as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State was rejected and the alternative upheld which states that there is a significant relationship between lecturers’ supervision of students as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State. This implies that a significant relationship exist between lecturers’ supervision of students as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings obtained on research question 1 on Table 1 indicated that there is a moderate and positive relationship between lecturers’ research publication as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State with ‘r’ as 0.574. Corresponding hypothesis 1 on Table 4 shows a significant relationship between lecturers’ research publication as an administrators’ promotion appraisal practice and lecturers’ job performances in public universities in Rivers State with t-ratio Transformation of 26.66 which was greater than the t-critical value of ±1.96. The findings is in tandem with Adeleke and Okoro (2020) who stated that administrators often prioritize research output as a key indicator of academic success and

contribution to knowledge generation within their institutions. These quantitative indicators provide administrators with tangible evidence of lecturers' scholarly contributions and impact within their respective fields. Also in support, Ogunbajo and Adewale (2019) opined that engagement in research enables lecturers to stay abreast of developments in their fields, deepen their expertise, and contribute to the advancement of knowledge. Through conducting research, lecturers develop critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, and subject matter expertise, which enrich their teaching and mentorship capabilities.

The findings obtained on research question 2 on Table 2 indicated that there is a moderate and positive relationship between lecturers' community services as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State with 'r' as 0.501. Hypothesis 2 on Table 5 shows a significant relationship between lecturers' community services as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State with t-ratio Transformation of 26.68 which was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 . The findings is in agreement with Eze and Chukwu (2018) who opined that community service as an appraisal practice holds significance in the evaluation framework of lecturers' job performances in academic institutions. This findings is also in tandem with Adeleke and Okoro (2020) who asserted that by working closely with local organizations, government agencies, and non-profit groups, lecturers demonstrate their commitment to social responsibility and community engagement.

The findings obtained on research question 3 on Table 3 indicated that there is a high and positive relationship between lecturers' supervision of students as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State with 'r' as 0.750. Hypothesis 3 on Table 6 shows a significant relationship between lecturers' supervision of students as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State with t-ratio Transformation of 26.69 which was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 . The findings is in agreement with Oluwaseun and Afolabi, 2019 (2019) who opined that the supervision of students serves as a key indicator of lecturers' commitment to academic excellence, students' success, and the mission of the university. This findings is also in tandem with Okonkwo and Ibrahim (2017), who averred that lecturers who actively supervise students' research endeavors enhance their own research profiles, publications, and scholarly contributions, thereby bolstering their academic reputation and standing within the university community.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that a high, positive and significant relationship exist between lecturers' research publication, lecturers' community services and lecturers' supervision of students as an administrators' promotion appraisal practice and lecturers' job performances in public universities in Rivers State. By implementing clear, transparent, and consistent promotion appraisal criteria that acknowledge these various facets of a lecturer's work, public universities in Rivers State can foster an enabling environment that motivates and supports academic excellence

Recommendations

1. Public universities in Rivers State should develop and implement clear and transparent promotion appraisal criteria that recognize and reward lecturers' research publications and contributions within their academic disciplines.
2. Universities should establish community engagement offices or units to coordinate and promote lecturers' involvement in community service initiatives, fostering stronger university-community partnerships.

3. Graduate Schools and Departments should provide mentorship programmes to ensure effective supervision and guidance for students, particularly at the postgraduate level, enhancing the quality of research and student development.

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